

1 **Biochar mitigates the postponed bioavailability of phthalic acid esters in the soil**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Observed nowadays wide pollution of the environment with microplastic and phthalic
21 acid esters (PAEs) (such as dimethyl phthalate, DMP; diethyl phthalate, DEP; dibutyl phthalate,
22 DBP; benzyl butyl phthalate, BBP; di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, DEHP and di-n-octyl phthalate,
23 DNOP) is a result of their increased production and usage. Weak bonding with polymer matrix
24 enables their easier mobilization in the environment and increased bioavailability. The aim of
25 the presented studies was the estimation of the fate of six priority PAEs in the soil-vegetable
26 system and the application of biochar to immobilize PAEs in the soil preventing their
27 bioavailability to lettuce. Both the acute (one full lettuce development period) and prolonged
28 effect (lettuce cultivated after 10 weeks from the first PAEs contamination) were estimated to
29 examine the long-time exposure under crop rotation. The addition of 1% of corn-derived
30 biochar immobilized PAEs in the soil efficiently (up to 4 times increased concentration) with
31 the following order: DBP<DEP<DMP<DEHP<DNOP<BBP. Bioavailable PAEs were
32 determined in lettuce roots (DMP, BBP, DEHP), and lettuce leaves (DEP, DBP, DNOP) but
33 the presence of biochar lowered their content. PAEs, although not available for lettuce, were
34 available for other organisms, confirming that the bioavailability or lack of nutrients is of great
35 importance in PAEs-polluted soil. In long-time experiments, without biochar amendment, all
36 PAEs were 3-12 times more bioavailable and were mainly accumulated in lettuce roots. The
37 biochar addition significantly reduces (1.5-11 times) PAEs bioavailability over time. However,
38 the PAEs content in roots remained significantly higher in samples with crop rotation compared
39 to samples where only lettuce was grown. The results confirmed that BC addition to the soil
40 reduces their bioavailability and mobility inside the plant, limiting their transport from roots to
41 leaves and reducing the exposure risk but confirming that lettuce leaves may be a safe food
42 when cultivated in PAEs-polluted soil.

43 **Keywords**

44 Phthalic acid esters; diethyl phthalate; di-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; di-n-octyl phthalate;

45 lettuce

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47 **1. Introduction**

48 Phthalic acid esters (PAEs) are very popular plasticizers used in industry and households
49 (Xiong and Pei, 2021). Dimethyl phthalate (DMP) and diethyl phthalate (DEP), are mostly used
50 as solvents in beauty products; dibutyl phthalate (DBP), benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP) and di-
51 (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) and di-n-octyl phthalate (DNOP) are commonly used as
52 plasticizers (Edwards et al., 2022). DEHP is one of the crucial plasticizers in the polymer
53 industry used in the production of PVC, where it may constitute up to 40-50% of the weight of
54 the product (Zhao et al., 2022). Additionally, DBP and DEHP are widely applied PAEs in
55 agricultural films, thus the literature data concentrate on DEP, DBP, and DEHP, mainly (Zhang
56 et al., 2021). PAEs' widespread use and weak interactions with the polymer matrix (hydrogen
57 bonds or by van der Waals forces (Hou et al., 2021)) make them common pollutants in all
58 environments: air, water, and soil. The main source of PAEs in the environment is plastic
59 products from where they are easily leached (Bi et al., 2021; Giuliani et al., 2020). PAEs
60 revealed undesired effects on human health (Giuliani et al., 2020), therefore, the United States
61 Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) identified DMP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP, and
62 DNOP as pollutants requiring priority control, and DEHP also was classified as a probable
63 human carcinogen (Hui et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021). In the environment, PAEs are dangerous
64 pollutants, because they may be taken up by plants from the soil (Table 1) and introduced into
65 the food chain. Soil contamination with PAEs is a huge problem in greenhouses and fields
66 where agricultural films are used. About 72% of DEHP migrates into soils during the entire life
67 cycle of plastic products resulting in even several mg/kg of DEHP determined in different soils
68 (Luo et al., 2023). Fruits and vegetables may be contaminated with PAEs and contaminated
69 food is the main source of human exposure to PAEs (Coltro et al., 2023). Meanwhile, PAEs
70 may be considered as indicators of microplastics in the environment (Yulin Chen et al., 2023).

71 The fate of the PAEs in the environment is governed mainly by the two processes:
72 biodegradation and adsorption. Various species of PAEs degrading bacteria were extracted from
73 various matrices, for example, *Achromobacter* strains from sewage sludge, *Agromyces* and
74 *Bacillus* from the soil, *Curvibacter* from sediments, *Providencia* from compost, and
75 *Pseudoxanthomonas* from bioreactors (Fan et al., 2023; Ou et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2023).
76 However, the rate of biodegradation of PAEs in the environment is low (Luo et al., 2023). For
77 sorption and immobilization of PAEs, biochar (BC) can be used. International Biochar Initiative
78 defines biochar as „solid material obtained from thermochemical conversion of biomass in an
79 oxygen-limited environment” (“IBI_Biochar_Standards_V2.1_Final.pdf,” n.d.). Biochar may
80 be obtained from agricultural wastes such as straw, nut shells, leaves, or manure, but also from
81 sewage sludge (Inyang et al., 2016). The possibility of producing biochar from various wastes
82 is a great advantage: these types of materials are cheap and easily available. Moreover, this
83 method of waste management may reduce the costs of their disposal. Processing biodegradable
84 waste instead of landfilling reduces the microbiological risk by eliminating pathogenic
85 microorganisms and reduces emissions of methane and other gases that are emitted from
86 landfills (Inyang et al., 2016; Malińska, 2012) which fulfills four Sustainable Development
87 Goals (Neogi et al., 2022).
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Table 1. The content of PAEs in the soil from different locations.

Matrix	Total PAEs	DMP	DEP	DBP	BBP	DEHP	DNOP	Reference
Soil [$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$]								
Soil (dry weight)	197	ND	ND	6.12	0.861	183	6.97	(Wei et al., 2020)
Soil	$\Sigma_5\text{PAEs}$ in topsoil	35–72	101–202	141–235		454–865	229–	(Hui et al., 2021)
	1860						490	
Soil	776	30.1	119	287	159	414	152	(Zhou et al., 2021)
Topsoil		20.9	204.5	81.5	15.9	329.2	ND	(Liu et al., 2010)
Surface soil from Beijing	310	10	10	90	50	110	60	(Cheng et al., 2015)
Deep soil from Beijing	200	10	20	40	50	80	40	(Cheng et al., 2015)
Urban soil	1369.3	23.5	23.4	521.7	11.7	765.3	23.5	(Wang et al., 2018)
Soil from greenhouse		34	113	552		396		(Chen et al., 2017)
Agricultural soils with plastic film mulching		140	340	1987	490	292	364	(K. Li et al., 2016)
Soil from the greenhouse in Beijing		8	20	440	4	380	2	(C. Li et al., 2016)
Soil in the neighborhood of phthalate-emitting plants				560	100	490		(Müller and Kördel, 1993)

90 ND- not detected

91

92 Biochars possess extended specific surface area and high sorption capacity (Monisha et
93 al., 2022) making them superior in various adsorption processes (Monisha et al., 2022; Patel et
94 al., 2019), and heavy metals from water or wastewater (Inyang et al., 2016). Additionally,
95 biochars are used as soil additives and their positive effect is confirmed by numerous studies.
96 They may increase the pH of acidic soils and cation exchange capacity (CEC) (Jaiswal et al.,
97 2014; Joseph et al., 2021), hold high soil organic matter (SOM) (Kamau et al., 2019), and
98 increase retention of various elements such as K, Mg, Ca, P, Mn, Cu, N, S, and Fe by sorbing
99 them and accumulating them in the topsoil (Wang et al., 2020). Biochar inhibits also the
100 evaporation of water from the soil thus keeping the soil moist (Gao et al., 2021). Another benefit
101 of using biochar as fertilizer is the stimulation of the development of soil fungi and bacteria
102 whose presence increases soil fertility (Dangi et al., 2020; Xiao et al., 2018).

103 The application of biochar as a fertilizer simultaneously as a sorbent of emerging
104 pollutants may solve two main problems: i) nutrient shortage, and ii) immobilization of the
105 toxic pollutants. In most of the studies, short-term effects are measured, but it seems interesting
106 to verify how will change the bioavailability of PAEs under crop rotation. The other questions
107 arose: are the PAEs efficiently immobilized onto biochar surface? How will crop rotation affect
108 the bioavailability of PAEs in biochar-amended soil? As the test organism, a common vegetable
109 - lettuce was chosen. Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.), the representative of the *Asteraceae* family
110 (Qiao et al., 2023), is a source of dietary fiber, vitamins (A, C, and E), phenols, carotenoids,
111 and microelements. In general, leafy vegetables tend to accumulate for example nitrate more
112 frequently than other vegetable crops (Shalaby, 2024).

113 Thus, the objective of the presented studies was the estimation of the bioavailability of
114 PAEs in the soil-vegetable system in biochar-amended soil under crop rotation. In the short-
115 time experiment, the effect of biochar amendment on PAEs' bioavailability in lettuce was
116 estimated. In the second step, the soil after lettuce cultivation was subjected to ecotoxicological

117 studies to examine the effect of PAEs polluted soil after biochar amendment and lettuce
118 cultivation. In the long-term experiment, in the PAEs polluted soil, other plants were planted,
119 and then lettuce was cultivated to verify the effect of prolonged PAEs exposure on the tested
120 organism.

121 2. Materials and methods

122 2.1. Chemicals and characterization methods

123 The certified reference standards of PAEs: DMP, DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP, DNOP
124 (Sigma-Aldrich, Poland), and deuterated phthalates (internal standards): bis(2-
125 ethylhexyl)phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄ (DEHP-3,4,5,6-d₄), dimethyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄, diethyl
126 phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄, and dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄ acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis,
127 MO, USA) were kept under stable conditions at -20 °C. A standard mixture was prepared from
128 individual stock standard solutions to obtain the concentration at 1 µg/mL in hexane. All other
129 working solutions for determining calibration curves (R^2 0.9969-0.9994), recoveries (97.17-
130 99.12%), limits of detection (LODs) (0.09-0.43 µg/kg), and limits of quantification (LOQs)
131 (0.30-1.43 µg/kg) were prepared by diluting the standard mixture in acetonitrile. Acetonitrile
132 and methanol (LCMS grade) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany); hexane and
133 ethyl acetate (HPLC grade) from POCH S.A. (Gliwice, Poland); anhydrous magnesium sulfate
134 (99.5 % powder; MgSO₄) and sodium chloride from Merck (Warszawa, Poland). For the
135 QuEChERS process, Septra C18-E (50 µm, 65Å), and Septra PSA sorbents were acquired from
136 Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). The details of the analytical procedure are in our latest
137 paper (Sokołowski et al., 2023).

138 Biochar obtained from corn cobs and stalks (*Zea mays*) and pyrolyzed at 600 °C in a
139 nitrogen atmosphere (630 cm³ min⁻¹) for 3 hours was tested for its physicochemical properties
140 such as pH, ash content, total organic carbon (TOC) analysis, C, H, and N content, surface
141 morphology, and characteristics by scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging, FT-IR

142 spectroscopy with attenuated total reflection (FTIR-ATR) spectroscopy, X-ray photoelectron
 143 spectroscopy (XPS), and Accelerated Surface Area and Porosimetry System (ASAP) analysis.

144 The pH of biochar was measured by a digital pH meter HQ430d Benchtop Single Input
 145 (HACH, USA). 2 g of biochar was mixed with 20 mL of distilled ultrapure water, shaken for
 146 24 h, and centrifuged. The ash content was determined as a difference in biochar mass before
 147 and after heating 1 g of BC to a temperature of 760 °C in the furnace (MagmaTherm, Poland)
 148 for 6 h. The carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen contents were determined by CHN/CHNS
 149 EuroEA3000 Elemental Analyser (EuroVector). The oxygen content was calculated from the
 150 difference in ash and C, H, and N content. Total organic carbon (TOC) was determined in
 151 Shimadzu SSM-5000A. The surface area and porosity were determined using ASAP 2420
 152 Analyzer (Micromeritics, USA). The specific surface area and pore volume are critical
 153 parameters in the use of biochar as a sorbent. BC surface morphology was observed via
 154 scanning electron microscope (SEM) imaging (Quanta 3D FEG FEI), whereas the presence of
 155 the surface functional groups was evidenced using FT-IR spectroscopy (Nicolet 8700A) and X-
 156 ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (analytical system UHV Prevac, Poland).

157 2.2. Pot experiment

158 The fate of PAEs in soil-vegetable systems was established using agricultural soil from
 159 Podborcze, Poland (50°41'47.5"N 22°50'41.3" E). The topsoil samples (0-20 cm) were air-
 160 dried, sieved (0.25 mm), homogenized, and divided into several groups (340 g each). The main
 161 properties of the applied soil are presented in Table 2.

162 Table 2. Characteristics of the applied soil.

location	type	Total organic carbon content [g/kg]	pH _{KCl}	N _{total} [g/kg]	P ¹ [mg/kg]	K ¹ [mg/kg]	Mg ² [mg/kg]	CEC [cmol(+)/kg]
Podborcze, Poland (50°41'47.5"N 22°50'41.3" E)	agricultural acidic brown soil developed from deep loess	2.986	5.3-6.2	4.9	59.3	346.9	73	7.12

163 ¹determined by the Egnea-Riehm method

164 ²determined by the Schachtschabel method

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166 The soil was characterized by medium available P content, whereas other nutrient content
167 was high (Mg) or very high (K). The content of organic carbon in the solid sample was 2.986
168 g/kg with 33.33 mg/L of total dissolved carbon fraction. The experiment consisted of two series
169 of samples. Control (uncultivated soil), soil spiked with 1 mL or 2 mL of PAEs mixture
170 containing 1 µg/mL of each tested compound were transferred into 500 mL glass containers
171 (12.5 cm diameter, 6.3 cm height), and tap water was added to reach 65% of the water-holding
172 capacity of the soil. A 1% addition of biochar was applied to estimate the effect of biochar
173 addition to soil on the fate and accumulation of PAEs. A 1% addition (corresponding to 30 t/ha)
174 of biochar is often applied (Guan et al., 2023) and is economically and practically justified. The
175 10 lettuce seeds (*Letuca sativa L.*) were placed in each container (except two controls). Each
176 experiment was run in triplicate. The samples were exposed to regular light/dark cycles (12:12
177 h) in Conviron GEN100 (temperature 22°C/18°C day/night, humidity 65%, watered twice a
178 week). In the first series, soil injected with phthalates was used and lettuce was planted on it.
179 The second series of samples was treated the same, but the soil used in the experiment was
180 spiked with 1 mL of PAEs mixture and then the different plants were grown on it for 10 weeks.
181 After this time lettuce was planted. This experiment was intended to simulate crop rotation and
182 show how the PAEs' bioavailability changes over time. After lettuce cultivation (6 weeks for
183 both experiments), the plants were carefully removed from the soil, and cut to separate roots
184 from the leaves. The subparts were firstly frozen in the freezer (-20°C, Liebherr) and lyophilized
185 in Alpha 1-2 LDplus (Christ) for further GC-MS/MS analysis.

186 Bioaccumulation factor (BAF) was used to estimate the hazard of PAEs in lettuce. BAF is
187 defined as the ratio of the concentration of a chemical in an organism part to its concentration
188 in the matrix, here soil, which was calculated according to the following equation:

189
$$\text{BAF} = C_{\text{roots or leaves}} / C_{\text{soil}},$$

190 where $C_{\text{roots/leaves}}$ are the concentration of PAEs in the roots or leaves of lettuce ($\mu\text{g/g}$) and C_{soil}
191 is the PAEs concentration in the soil ($\mu\text{g/g}$) (Ai et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2021).

192 The toxicity of soil extracts in water (1:10 wt:wt) mixed for 24 h (120 rpm) after the
193 lettuce harvesting was performed according to the Microtox® and Collembolan test procedures
194 (Domene et al., 2007; Domínguez et al., 2023) to establish the effect of BC presence in
195 immobilization and bioavailability of PAEs in the soil.

196 **2.3. Statistical analysis**

197 For the quantitative analysis of PAEs, the internal standard calibration method was
198 employed. The samples were tested in the absence of individual PAEs or internal standards.
199 The presented method of PAEs determination in environmental samples was validated in terms
200 of the limit of detection (LOD), the limit of quantification (LOQ), linearity, specificity,
201 precision, and accuracy (Dybowski and Dawidowicz, 2018). All data are expressed as the mean
202 \pm standard deviation of three replicates. Single-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used
203 to analyze the data. Probability values at $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

204 **3. Results and discussion**

205 **3.1. Physicochemical characteristics of tested biochar**

206 The obtained biochar (Table 3) was characterized by high pH and low ash content which
207 is consistent with the literature data when plant feedstock is used (Rafiq et al., 2016). Elemental
208 analysis revealed that C was the main element (76.68%) in biochar and was present in the form
209 of organic compounds (TOC 818.42 mg/g). Biochar possessed medium extended surface area
210 ($89.3 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) The total BET surface area of biochars was largely determined by 10-20 nm
211 mesopores but the mean pore diameter was calculated to be 1.99 nm. The shape of the N_2
212 sorption–desorption isotherms followed the type II IUPAC classification (He et al., 2011)
213 indicating a multilayer adsorption process occurred on a uniform and developed porous media

214 (Jing et al., 2018). The porous structure of the biochar is crucial for example for the DEP
 215 adsorption where the pore-filling mechanism of adsorption onto the biochar surface was
 216 established (Jing et al., 2018).

217 Table 3. The physicochemical properties of BC obtained from corn stalks.

pH	Ash (%)	C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	O (%)	H/C (-)	(O+N)/C (-)	O/C (-)	TOC (mg/g)	S _{BET} (m ² /g)	V _p (cm ³ /g)	D (nm)
9.6	14.12	76.68	2.71	1.3	5.18	0.035	0.085	0.068	818.42	89.307	0.03199	1.99

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219 The FT-IR spectrum (Fig.1A) confirmed the presence of various functional groups on the
 220 surface of biochar. The peak at 3432 cm⁻¹ came from stretching vibrations of bonds O-H and
 221 N-H and confirmed the presence of O-H and N-H bonds (Misra et al., 2007). Two peaks at 2923
 222 cm⁻¹ and 2870 cm⁻¹ came from asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the aliphatic
 223 CH₂ groups (Viana et al., 2012) in biopolymers (Fang et al., 2015). Aromatic C=C bonds or
 224 C=O bonds and quinone C were depicted by the peak at 1630 cm⁻¹ (Yang et al., 2012). The
 225 presence of the CN and CO groups was also evidenced by the peak at 1063 cm⁻¹ (Anjos et al.,
 226 2021). These results suggested that biochar contains a large number of oxygen functional
 227 groups (Fang et al., 2015). In the studies on DEP adsorption (Jing et al., 2018), it was
 228 established that O-containing functional groups were of great importance. Firstly, the
 229 adsorption of DEP occurred via O-containing functional groups (van der Waals forces and H-
 230 bonding), secondly, the abundance of O-containing groups may hinder the adsorption through
 231 the formed three-dimensional water clusters (Jing et al., 2018). The presence of O- but also N-
 232 containing functional groups favored the adsorption of less hydrophobic PAEs (like DEP) (Sun
 233 et al., 2012). Thus for adsorption and immobilization, two main parameters are crucial: i)
 234 extended available surface area, and ii) increased polarity (presence of surface O- or N-
 235 containing functional groups) (Xu et al., 2021) suggesting that BC addition to the soil may
 236 immobilize PAEs through adsorption effectively.

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241 Fig. 1. A) The FT-IR spectrum of tested biochar; B) XPS survey; C) XPS C 1s peak; D) XPS
 242 O 1s peak; E) SEM image of tested biochar.

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244 BC surface was composed of C (87at%), O (9.9 at%), K (1.9 at%), P, and Si (0.6 at%
 245 each) that was established from XPS studies (Fig. 1B). The XPS spectrum (Fig. 1C) also
 246 confirmed the presence of different carbon forms on the surface of the corn-derived biochar.
 247 The most present form of carbon was the carbon bonded to hydrogen (C-H), which confirmed
 248 the peak at 284.7 eV (Koinuma et al., 2013) (37.4 at%). The other abundant carbon forms were
 249 C=C sp² (peak at 284.14 eV (Rabchinskii et al., 2020); 27.1 at%) and C-C sp³ (peak at 285.25
 250 eV (Koinuma et al., 2013); 16.1 at%). The XPS spectrum indicated also that in this biochar
 251 carbon was also bonded in forms of C-OH (peak at 286.01 eV; 7.3 at%), C-O-C (peak at 286.81
 252 eV; 2.8 at%), C=O (peak at 287.32 eV; 1 at%), O=C-O (peak at 287.9 eV; 1.8 at%), O=C-OH
 253 (peak at 288.66 eV; 1.6 at%) (Radaelli et al., 2016), CO₃²⁻ (peak at 289.54 eV; 3.4 at%), and
 254 HCO₃⁻ (peak at 290.67 eV; 1.4 at%) (Chiang et al., 2017). Oxygen in biochar (Fig. 1D) was
 255 present as aliphatic hydroxyl groups C-OH (peak at 532.7 eV (Baltrusaitis et al., 2007); 30.5
 256 at%). The presence of the carbonyl oxygen (O=C) was implied by the peak at 531.67 eV
 257 (Rabchinskii et al., 2018), and it was the second most abundant form of oxygen (27.9 at%) on
 258 the surface of biochar. Aromatic hydroxyl groups were confirmed by the peak at 533.7 eV; and

259 19.9 at%. The other oxygen forms in this biochar were oxide anion O^{2-} (peak at 530.82 eV; 14.2
260 at%) and adsorbed water and oxygen (peak at 534.63 eV, 7.4 at%) (Oh et al., 2014). O-
261 containing surface functional groups are the most important when considering the adsorption
262 of various substances onto biochar surface

263 Scanning electron microscope imaging was used to observe the biochar surface
264 morphology. SEM images (Fig. 1 E) indicated that the surface was not uniform with a lot of
265 channels and pores. The morphology of the tested biochar resembled the structure of the
266 feedstock (Kończak et al., 2021). This fact is also important for the use of biochar as a sorbent
267 for removing PAEs from soil.

268 **3.2. Analysis of the fate of PAEs in soil-vegetable systems in short-term experiment**

269 According to the literature data, PAEs like other organic pollutants when present in soil
270 may affect the productivity of the crops and vegetables due to the induced oxidative stress and
271 may be bioaccumulated revealing the environmental and human hazard (Xu et al., 2021). The
272 presence of PAEs at a tested concentration in BC-amended soil decreased the fresh mass of
273 lettuce leaves, which are the eatable parts of the product (Fig. 2A). The effect on the roots was
274 not, however, significant. The presence of PAEs favored untypical root devolvement. The roots
275 were shorter but more branched which may indicate that they were looking for water or
276 nutrients such as sulfate, phosphate, iron, and nitrate. The root growth may be also disturbed by
277 changes in the synthesis and sensitivity of various hormones e.g. cytokinins, auxins, and
278 ethylene. These compounds are known root growth regulators (López-Bucio et al., 2003). A
279 significant, more than doubled increase in the weight of wheat grain in the DBP-polluted and
280 biochar-amended soil (Xu et al., 2021) was noted implying that the positive effect of biochar is
281 characteristic for both biochar properties and cultivated plants.

282 Different behavior of the PAEs in the lettuce-soil system was noted (Fig. 2B). The
283 presence of BC significantly enhanced the immobilization of all tested PAEs in the soil thus

284 hindering the bioavailability of the tested compound. In BC-amended soil, the number of
 285 immobilized PAEs was changed in the following order: DBP < DEP < DMP < DEHP < DNOP
 286 \approx BBP. Similar results of the highest adsorption capacity for DNOP were noted in the studies
 287 (Chen et al., 2019) using mesoporous cellulose biochar.

288 The effect of both PAEs type and concentration was observed. In PAEs polluted soil
 289 without additional treatment at higher concentrations in the lettuce roots DMP, BBP, and DEHP
 290 were noted. At the same time in the lettuce leaves higher concentrations of DEP, DBP, and
 291 DNOP were determined. BC amendment resulted in bioaccumulation of BBP in the lettuce
 292 roots or DMP, DEP, DBP, and DNOP in the lettuce leaves implying that the bioavailability of
 293 tested compounds was changed. Increased initial concentrations of DMP, DEP, and BBP did
 294 not result in a significant increase of determined compounds in both parts of the lettuce.

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Fig. 2. A) Fresh mass of lettuce in control sample and BC-amended PAEs polluted soil; B) % distribution of PAEs in BC-amended PAEs polluted soil; content of individual PAEs in tested lettuce roots and leaves: C) DMP; D) DEP; E) DBP; F) BBP; G) DEHP; H) DNOP; I) Microtox® test results; J) Collembolan tests results. Dash line represents the content of PAEs in control soil, % distribution was calculated on the comparison to blank soil samples; means followed by the same letter within the series indicate no significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

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A higher content of DMP was noted in the lettuce roots than in leaves when cultivated without the addition of BC. In BC-amended soil leaves were the main sink for DMP. An increase in the content of DMP resulted in lowered content in the roots and slightly increased content of

309 DMP in leaves in the soil without BC addition. The presence of BC in the soil slightly affected
310 the root content of DMP, with no statistically important difference in the DMP content in the
311 leaves. Leaves were the main part of lettuce where DEP and DBP were noted, and BC-
312 amendment lowered the content of DEP and DBP in all parts of the lettuce. BBP and DEHP
313 were determined mainly in the roots of lettuce than in leaves both at lower and higher initial
314 BBP content and with or without BC addition. BC effect was mostly seen when a higher initial
315 DEHP concentration was applied. BC lowered the bioavailability of DEHP. DNOP was noted
316 mainly in the leaves and BC addition increased the content of DNOP in the leaves. Increased
317 pollution of soil with BBP increased significantly the content in the lettuce roots and slightly in
318 the lettuce leaves but considering that the edible part of lettuce are leaves lower environmental
319 hazard can be observed. Similar competitive adsorption between DBP and DEHP was observed
320 in the studies (Abdoul Magid et al., 2021).

321 The values of the BAF are presented in Table 4. The highest BAF value was calculated
322 for soil with 1% BC addition, which indicates that BC adsorbed PAEs effectively thus reducing
323 their bioavailability. What is interesting, the lowest BAF values were noted for DEP, DBP, and
324 DEHP in the lettuce roots in biochar-amended soil confirming that lettuce leaves may be a safe
325 food when cultivated using DEHP-containing agricultural films.

326 The BAF factor was used to estimate the affinity of the PAEs toward soil or different
327 parts of the lettuce. It was established that the key parameter affecting the environmental
328 behavior of PAEs are their water solubility and $\log K_{ow}$ (based on the values from the National
329 Library of Medicine, National Centre for Biotechnology Information, PubChem). It was
330 established that $\log K_{ow}$ as the measure of hydrophobicity was affecting the partitioning of
331 PAEs. Statistically important correlations between $\log BAF$ and $\log K_{ow}$ were noted for the
332 content of PAEs in leaves using an enriched solution or content of PAEs in BC-amended soil
333 ($p < 0.05$). More important statistically was the relation between $\log BAF$ and $\log K_{ow}$ of PAEs

334 noted in the lettuce roots that were independent of the initial concentration of PAEs ($p < 0.02$ for
 335 30 ng/g and $p < 0.01$ for 60 ng/g). However, the BC amendment affected the concentration of
 336 highly hydrophobic PAEs in the lettuce leaves ($p < 0.02$).

337

338 Table 4. Effects of biochar on bioconcentration factors (BAF) of PAEs in lettuce roots and
 339 leaves.

	BAF					
	DMP	DEP	DBP	BBP	DEHP	DNOP
Roots [30 ng/g]	0.0333c	0.0668b	0.0764b	0.1223d	0.1261b	0.1466b
Leaves [30 ng/g]	0.0138a	0.1079c	0.0955c	0.0631a	0.0817a	0.1952c
Roots [60 ng/g]	0.0183b	0.0501a	0.0676a	0.0977c	0.1741c	0.1856c
Leaves [60 ng/g]	0.0169b	0.0481a	0.0797b	0.0847b	0.1324b	0.0815a
Soil with 1% BC	1.5456c	1.1875d	1.0590c	2.5484e	2.0496c	2.4900e
Roots [30 ng/g] +BC	0.0173a	0.0399a	0.0570a	0.1008b	0.0841a	0.0790a
Leaves [30 ng/g]+BC	0.0193b	0.0494c	0.0769b	0.0760a	0.0848a	0.3244d
Roots [60 ng/g] +BC	0.0234c	0.0444b	0.0594s	0.2540d	0.1301c	0.1562b
Leaves [60 ng/g]+BC	0.0174a	0.0518c	0.0602a	0.1156c	0.1124b	0.2756c

340 Different letters indicate significant differences between the BC amendments and control at the same
 341 PAEs concentrations ($P < 0.05$) (Xu et al., 2021).

342 The positive effect of biochar presence on the fate of PAEs was noted in the literature
 343 (Guan et al., 2023). DEHP is a widely tested compound (Guan et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2023).
 344 1% biochar prepared from agricultural wastes (corn straw biochar (BC) pyrolyzed at 600 °C)
 345 loaded with DEHP degrading bacteria *Arthrobacter* sp. JQ-1 increased the degradation rate of
 346 DEHP by 30.9% which was ascribed to the pH neutralizing effect of BC (presence of the surface
 347 alkaline functional groups, e.g. lactone group, –OH, –COO– favoring the enzymatic activity of
 348 alkaline phosphatase) and increased available surface area for simultaneous adsorption of
 349 DEHP and bacteria (Guan et al., 2023). The presence of pollutants (like PAEs) is mitigated by
 350 the increased nutrient bioavailability. Biochar, as a biological stimulant (Guan et al., 2023), is
 351 the source of available nutrients, both organic and inorganic, and the porous surface is a habitat
 352 for naturally occurring bacteria that may involve PAEs in their metabolism. It was observed

353 that the presence of biochar may significantly reduce the bioavailability of PAEs which was
354 confirmed by the studies on BC effect (1% and 5%) on DBP fate in rice paddy soils (Xu et al.,
355 2021). BC in the soil increases the bioavailability of nutrients: C, N, P, K, and Si (Xu et al.,
356 2021) which were supplemented with BC addition as confirmed in XPS studies (0.6 at% of P,
357 1.9% K, and 0.6%Si) and CHN analysis (N: 1.3%). Increased bioavailability of nutrients is
358 connected with the increased enzymatic activity followed by increased amylose and
359 amylopectin or amino acids content (as the result of better N utilization) (Xu et al., 2021). The
360 presence of pores and the negative charges (resulting from the presence -OH, -COOH, and
361 small alkyl chains -CH₃) increased nutrient retention (NO₃⁻ and HPO₄²⁻/H₂PO₄⁻ and DOC) in
362 biochar-amended soil (Gul et al., 2015). Inhibition of PAEs in the soil may involve several
363 interactions depending both on BC and PAEs characteristics. The main mechanisms for
364 hydrophobic substance adsorption in the environment are hydrophobic partitioning and π - π
365 EDA interactions that are observed especially for BC obtained at higher temperatures (Jing et
366 al., 2018). BC pyrolyzed at lower temperatures or PAEs with lower hydrophobicity/higher
367 polarity will be adsorbed with the participation of van der Waals forces and H-bonds.
368 Summarizing, PAEs sorption is governed by chemisorption: DMP, DEP, and DBP were
369 adsorbed by BC surface mainly through π - π electron-donor-acceptor (EDA) interactions (due
370 to the presence of aromatic sheets in BC (Sun et al., 2012)). In the case of BBP and DNOP,
371 both hydrophobic and π - π EDA interactions were involved whereas DEHP - mainly *via*
372 hydrophobic interaction (Chen et al., 2019).

373 The other factor affecting the fate of PAEs in the soil-vegetable system was the presence
374 of BC-derived DOC (Sun et al., 2012). The decomposition of PAEs in the soil may be ascribed
375 to two main processes: i) microbial activity, and ii) reactivity of photogenerated reactive oxygen
376 species (ROS) from biochar during light irradiation. In the studies (Fang et al., 2017), it was
377 confirmed that irradiation of biochar by UV and simulated solar light induced the formation of

378 *OH (formed from biochar), ¹O₂ (from DOM in biochar), and Persistent Free Radicals (PFRs)
379 that mediate the formation of O₂⁻, H₂O₂ and *OH (Fang et al., 2015) which participate with e⁻
380 in the formation of O₂^{*-} similarly to DOM (Fang et al., 2017) and degrades DEP efficiently
381 (Fang et al., 2015). For example, the calculated second-order reaction rate constant for DEP
382 degradation with *OH was calculated to be 1.96 × 10⁹ M⁻¹s⁻¹ (Fang et al., 2017). In summary,
383 biochar with high DOM content is a source of ¹O₂, whereas biochar containing lots of surface
384 bound-PFRs produces mainly *OH under light irradiation (Fang et al., 2017). It was observed
385 that in general, higher organic matter content, lower pH, and less humus in the rhizosphere
386 favored DEHP hydrolysis (Yijie Chen et al., 2023).

387 In the environment, BC is affected by several processes such as sun irradiation inducing
388 photolysis and hydrolysis and leading to biochar aging (Krzyszczak et al., 2022). Aged BC
389 behaves differently from pristine material and it was observed that aged/oxidized BC surface
390 was not prone to DEP adsorption due to the competition with formed three-dimensional water
391 clusters on biochar surface blocking accessible sites and decreasing the H-bonding between
392 DEP and BC (Jing et al., 2018). In our studies, the results observed for DEP were consistent
393 with the literature, and BC amendment revealed the same results as obtained without BC which
394 was especially seen when the higher initial DEP concentration was used.

395 **3.2. Ecotoxicity studies**

396 Although the physicochemical properties of fresh BC may be used for the prediction of
397 its behavior in the environment, any aging processes will change BC's fate significantly. After
398 6 weeks that was established for lettuce cultivation, the toxicity tests of soil extracts were
399 performed. It was hypothesized that biochar-induced changes in soil (available nutrients, DOC,
400 surface area, and surface charge) can alter the activities of soil microorganisms (Gul et al.,
401 2015). The toxicity studies (Fig. 2 I) revealed some interesting data. Firstly, the presence of
402 PAEs in the soil after 6 weeks possessed zero to low toxicity to *Aliivibrio fischeri* (up to 20%

403 of bioluminescence inhibition, which is a limit for establishing the toxicity). Cultivation of the
404 lettuce increased the toxicity slightly (up to 25%). The addition of BC did not affect toxicity
405 but in the sample, after the cultivation of lettuce in the BC-amended soil the toxicity was the
406 highest which may indicate that although PAEs were not available for lettuce, they were
407 available for other organisms. A deeper analysis of the toxicity of soil extracts after lettuce
408 cultivation to soil organisms *Folsomia candida* (Fig. 2J) revealed that the cultivation of the
409 lettuce in PAEs-contaminated soil with 1% BC addition impacted, however, the survival of
410 *Folsomia candida* (whereas the reproduction not) confirming that the bioavailability or lack of
411 nutrients is of great importance in PAEs-polluted soil.

412 **3.3. Fate of PAEs in the lettuce-soil system in long-term experiment**

413 The lettuce that grew on soil previously used to grow other plants achieved greater
414 weight in samples with PAEs and the addition of BC (Fig. 2A). The mass of both roots and
415 leaves was significantly higher. Additionally, the lettuce roots from the control sample after 10
416 weeks were the lightest among all samples, whereas the leaves mass from the sample with PAEs
417 and biochar addition were the highest. The bioavailability of PAEs changes over time as was
418 observed in the samples with soil previously used for planting other crops. In all samples, both
419 without and with BC addition, all tested compounds achieved higher concentrations in lettuce
420 roots than in the leaves. In samples without BC amendment, all PAEs were much more
421 bioavailable and were mainly accumulated in lettuce roots. In samples with crop rotation DMP
422 concentration in the lettuce roots was 12 times higher than in samples in which lettuce was
423 sown immediately after pollution with phthalates. For other compounds, these differences were
424 smaller but all PAEs were determined in higher concentrations in samples after crop rotation
425 (4.79 times for DEP, 4.29 times for DBP, 3.1 times for BBP, 3.43 times for DEHP, and 3.03
426 times for DNOP). Differences between PAEs content in lettuce leaves in the samples from the
427 two series were not so significant. Only the DMP content was 19 times higher and the DEHP

428 content was 4.26 times higher in samples with crop rotation compared to samples without. The
429 biochar addition significantly reduces PAEs bioavailability over time. What is worth stressing,
430 the BC amendment reduces the concentrations of all tested PAEs both in the roots and leaves
431 of lettuce. However, the PAEs content in roots remained significantly higher in samples with
432 crop rotation compared to samples where only lettuce was grown. In the case of lettuce leaves
433 BC addition gives much better results. Only DMP and DEHP are present in higher
434 concentrations in samples after crop rotation, while the concentration of the other compounds
435 was significantly reduced. DEP content was reduced 8.69 times compared to samples without
436 BC and 3.1 times compared to samples with BC but without crop rotation. Similar results were
437 obtained for DBP: its concentration was reduced 2.3 times compared to samples without BC
438 and 1.55 times compared to samples with BC but without crop rotation. BBP and DNOP were
439 two compounds that in samples without crop rotation reached higher concentrations in lettuce
440 leaves as a result of BC addition to the soil, whereas in the samples with crop rotation and BC
441 amendment, their content was much lower. BBP content was reduced 6.84 times compared to
442 samples without BC and 2.34 times compared to samples with BC but without crop rotation.
443 DNOP content was reduced 9.44 times compared to samples without BC and 11.2 times
444 compared to samples with BC but without crop rotation.

445 These results show that PAEs bioavailability changes over time. When the soil was
446 contaminated with phthalates some time ago, they can be much more easily taken up by plants.
447 They are still accumulated in the roots to a much greater extent. However, BC addition to the
448 soil reduces their bioavailability and additionally reduces their mobility inside the plant,
449 limiting their transport from roots to leaves, which reduces the risk of exposure to their effects
450 when eating leafy vegetables like lettuce.

451 **4. Conclusions**

452 The addition of BC into the soil may affect the fate of various contaminants not only by
453 their inhibition but also by biotransformation. In the presented studies, it was established that
454 PAEs may be determined mainly in the lettuce roots (DMP, BBP, DEHP), and lettuce leaves
455 (DEP, DBP, DNOP) but the addition of 1% of BC lowered the content of PAEs noted in the
456 selected organ (DMP in roots, DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP both in the roots and leaves) but only
457 increased the content of DNOP. Increased concentration of PAEs in BC-amended soil may
458 increase (BBP) or lower their content in the lettuce roots (DMP, DEP DBP, DNOP) or leaves
459 (DNOP). The results indicate that the effect of BC addition to soil on PAEs fate is both
460 dependent on BC and PAEs characteristics. Although 1% biochar addition may be
461 recommended as an effective tool for reducing the bioavailability of PAEs in the lettuce-soil
462 system, it has to be considered, however, that PAEs immobilized in the soil may still pose a
463 detrimental effect on the soil organisms as it was observed for *Folsomia candida*, stressing that
464 the bioavailability or lack of nutrients is of great importance in PAEs-polluted soil. In long-
465 time experiments, without biochar amendment, all PAEs were 3-12 times more bioavailable
466 and were mainly accumulated in lettuce roots. The biochar addition significantly reduced (1.5-
467 11 times) PAEs bioavailability over time. However, the PAEs content in roots remained
468 significantly higher in samples with crop rotation compared to samples where only lettuce was
469 grown. The results confirmed that BC addition to the soil reduces their bioavailability and
470 additionally reduces their mobility inside the plant, limiting their transport from roots to leaves
471 and reducing the exposure risk but confirming that lettuce leaves may be a safe food when
472 cultivated using DEHP-containing agricultural films.

473 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

474 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
475 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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